

ABSTRACT BOOKLET

ISAJ-2015

6th ISAJ Symposium on
Recent Advancement in Science and Technology

December 4th, 2015
Auditorium, Embassy of India,
Tokyo Japan

INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

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The Ambassador of India to Japan

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डा. भार. चिदम्बरम्
भारत सरकार के प्रमुख वैज्ञानिक सलाहकार
एवं
डी.ए.इ. - होमो सायन्स प्रोफेसर
Dr. R. Chidambaram
Principal Scientific Advisor to the Govt. of India
&
DAE - Homi Bhabha Professor

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Message

I am very happy that this year the Indian Scientists Association in Japan is organizing the 6th ISAJ Symposium on 'Recent Advances in Science and Technology' and the encouraging feature is the continuing support ISAJ gets from the Indian Embassy, whose Auditorium will be the venue of the meeting.

India places great value on its scientific cooperation with Japan and happily this is continuously increasing. Very recently I had the pleasure of being present at the inauguration of the DALLAB, at IIT Delhi, which is a joint effort of the Department Bio Technology and AIST, Tsukuba .

I am sure ISAJ will continue to play a catalyst role in increasing the scientific cooperation between our two great countries.

I wish the Symposium all success.

R. Chidambaram
(R. Chidambaram)
20th November, 2015

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Ambassador of India

Message

MESSAGE

I am very happy to know that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is holding its 6th symposium. It gives me a great pleasure to join you and deliver the inaugural address. I fondly remember my brief interaction recently with the Indian Science and Technology minister Dr. Harsh Vardhan who visited Japan several weeks ago.

I look forward to strengthening bilateral cooperation among Japanese and Indian science and technology institutes. Together, we could prepare a new ecosystem to develop and innovate for the betterments of our societies. At JST, we are already working on several bilateral collaborations with India under the existing Japanese collaborative frameworks such as the Strategic International Research Cooperative Program and Science and Technology Research Partnership for Sustainable Development (SATREPS). In addition, our Sakura Science Plan invited around 300 young prominent Indian researchers and high school students to Japan this year, and they experienced Japan's science and technology. We are also developing India-specific programs and calling for joint proposals with Indian institutions. Recognizing the importance of our cooperation, I am glad to inform you that JST has now opened a liaison office in New Delhi.

Looking at the program, I am glad to note that ISAJ symposium is providing the opportunity for young Indian researchers here to appreciate some of the frontier research activities in Japan in addition to the high-level interactions among senior scientists from both countries.

I wish a successful and memorable ISAJ symposium.

A handwritten signature in black ink, which reads 'Hamaguchi Michinari'.

HAMAGUCHI Michinari, M.D., Ph.D.

President, Japan Science and Technology Agency

MESSAGE

I would like, on behalf of the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS), to extend my heartiest congratulations to all of the distinguished participants of this Indian Scientists Association in Japan 6th Symposium.

Since its establishment in 1932, JSPS has been Japan's core funding agency supporting scientific research. As you all may well know, promotion of international scientific cooperation has always been one of JSPS's main areas of involvement. Particular emphasis is placed on exchanges with India, and over more than 20 years JSPS has been carrying out various exchange programs in fields of the natural sciences with your Department of Science and Technology, DST. As for the collaboration in the fields of humanities and social sciences, I am pleased that JSPS concluded memoranda of understanding with the Indian Council of Historical Research, ICHR and the Indian Council of Social Science Research, ICSSR last year.

These new partnerships mark the start of JSPS's bilateral exchange with India in more total and comprehensive manner. I hope ISAJ will welcome Indian scholars and researchers visiting Japan under our new exchange schemes.

Taking the liberty of today's opportunity, I wish to introduce an alumni association of former Indian JSPS Fellows. The Indian JSPS Alumni Association, IJAA, was launched in 2006 as the sixth official JSPS alumni association. It was the first alumni association to be established in Asia and also the first to be located in a country without a JSPS overseas office. IJAA is now one of the world's most active JSPS alumni associations, despite the fact that there is no JSPS office in India to assist it. We are proud of the self-motivation and passion that IJAA members instill in their alumni activities. I am sure that both IJAA and ISAJ will play important role on bridging research communities of two countries.

This is the sixth in the series of this symposium focusing on "Recent Advances in Science and Technology". Science and Technology is, needless to say, among the fields currently attracting a high level of worldwide attention. I look forward to seeing this Symposium be the milestone for further advancement of this field through an active exchange between researchers of Japan and India.

Dr. Yasuhiro Iye

Executive Director, JSPS

Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

I, on behalf of the ISAJ, warmly welcome all the guests and delegates to the 6th Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) on Recent Advances in Science and Technology.

Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ), a 6-year old Non Profit Organization (NPO), was created at the end of 2008 by coming together of many Indian scientists working in Japan. Formally inaugurated by Prof. R. Chidambaram, Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India in January 2009, in the presence of His Excellency the then Ambassador of India, it has grown into a registered NPO with its functional chapters spreading all over Japan. ISAJ has been focusing on networking among Indian scientists in Japan by organizing regular seminars, free discussions and networking at all sites.

After five successful annual symposia at the Main Auditorium, Embassy of India, Japan, I am very happy to welcome you to the sixth one today at the same place with due thanks to the Embassy of India for their generous support and cooperation. As almost a tradition set up in last 5 years, we make this event an interdisciplinary to allow wide participation and interactions. I firmly believe that this is a unique opportunity for all of us to learn beyond our specialized boundaries to innovate our thoughts and research outcomes. I am aware that besides the plenary and invited talks, free interactions over the poster presentations by young researchers that have been the highlight in all symposia were greatly enjoyed.

I am grateful to our guests, members and participants for their efforts to organize and contribute to this event. I sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium that will inspire India-Japan collaborations and friendships along with developing stronger ties in Science and Technology between the two countries.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Chairman
ISAJ

Conveners welcome message

It has been a great pleasure for us to convene the 6th ISAJ symposium. It is an honor and privilege to have with us high-level dignitaries, top scientists and young researchers from Japan and India as well as other nations. It also gives us immense pleasure to recognize the growing collaborations between India and Japan under bilateral as well as multilateral frameworks. We hope our efforts in developing new technologies and new science frontiers would help us to meet the demands of the growing populations of the world and future betterments of our societies.

India and Japan have historical relationships through exchanges of culture and heritage. With rapid progresses in science and technology, Japan is established as one of the leading centers in the world for scientific research. This excellent research environment has already benefited many of us. By further strengthening the growing scientific collaborations between Japan and India, we can address some of the global challenges and human securities. The unprecedented rate of recent global developments has increased pressures on the Earth environment and has been affecting the well-being of our societies. Fortunately, we are in a very opportunistic time when modern technologies are helping us to monitor parts of earth environment that were otherwise inaccessible a few decades ago. We hope through this initiative, we are able to provide a platform for Indian and Japanese experts and young researchers to exchange ideas and develop stronger collaborations.

Swadhin Behera

Mahendra Kumar

PROGRAM		
9:00 - 9:15	Registration	
9:15 - 9:20	LIGHTING of the LAMP	
9:20 - 9:30	Welcome Address	Sunil Kaul, ISAJ Chairman Swadhin Behera, Symposium Convener
9:30 – 10:00	INAUGURAL SESSION	
	Guest of Honor	The Ambassador of India to Japan
	Guest of Honor	Michinari Hamaguchi, President, JST, Japan
	Guest of Honor	Yasuhiro Iye, Executive Director, JSPS, Japan
10:00 - 10:30	Keynote	Asahiko Taira, President, JAMSTEC, Japan <i>“Frontier of marine science and technology - the Role of JAMSTEC -“</i>
10:30 - 10:35	Vote of Thanks Alok Singh, ISAJ Vice-Chairman	
10:35 - 10:40	GROUP PHOTO	
10:40 - 11:00	COFFEE BREAK	
	PLENARY SESSION 1 Chairs: Sunil Kaul and Swadhin Behera	
11:00- 11:20	Plenary	Koichi Tsuchiya, Director, Research Center for Strategic Materials, NIMS, Japan <i>“Materials technology for safe and secure social infrastructures”</i>
11:20 - 11:40	Plenary	Tomohiro Tamura, Director, Bioproduction Research Institute, AIST, Japan <i>“Efficient production of active form of vitamin D3 by microbial conversion”</i>
11:40 - 12:00	Invited	Junji Urakawa, KEK, Japan <i>“Status of Delhi light source project with R&D at KEK”</i>

12:00 - 12:40	LUNCH & POSTER SESSION
12:40 - 13:40	POSTER SESSION Chairs: Venkata Ratnam and Baiju Nair
	PLENARY SESSION 2 Chairs: Sakthi Kumar and Mamoru Mitsuishi
13:40 – 13:50	Manako Tanaka, Tokyo University of Arts, Japan <i>“Nondestructive study of Japanese iron artifacts using pulsed neutron imaging for evaluating crystallographic texture and microstructure”</i>
13:50 – 14:00	Satyaban Ratna, JAMSTEC, Japan <i>“Impact of the moisture variability on the Indian summer monsoon rainfall”</i>
14:00 – 14:10	Swastibrata Bhattacharya, Yokohama National University, Japan <i>“First principles based phase field crystal model”</i>
14:10 – 14:20	P.K Hashim, The University of Tokyo, Japan <i>“ Self-assembly of siRNA embedded protein for ‘Artificial Viruses’</i>
14:20 – 14:30	A Maya Nandkumar, Sree Chitra Tirunal Institute for Medical Sciences and Technology, India <i>“Microbial biofilms and medical devices”</i>
14:30 – 15:30	SELECTED POSTERS 1 Chairs: Manish Biyani, Kedarnath Mahapatra and Renu Wadhwa 12 short oral presentations (5min each) selected from posters: P03, P04, P08, P10, P12, P14, P15, P16, P17, P19, P21 and P24
15:30 – 15:50	COFFEE BREAK
15:50 – 16:50	SELECTED POSTERS 2 Chairs: Atsushi Suzuki, Samik Ghosh and Mahendra Kumar 12 short oral presentations (5min each) selected from posters: P25, P27, P28, P30, P31, P32, P34, P35, P36, P37, P39 and P40

PLENARY SESSION 3		
Chair: Alok Singh		
16:50-17:10	Plenary	Eiji Abe, Dept of Materials, U. of Tokyo “A new era of electron microscopy for materials science”
17:10-17:30	Guest Speaker	Kazunori Higuchi, International Program Department, JSPS “Overview of JSPS and its international collaborative program”
17:30 – 17:40	Concluding Session Swadhin Behera and Mahendra Kumar	
17:40 -18:30	CULTURAL PROGRAM 1. Padma Odishi Dance Group: Solo and group performances by Akane Hoshino, Ayako Koyasu and Nami Wakou. 2. Japan Dance School (JDS) Kids Japanese performance SAKURA 3. Solo Indian folk dance by Manasvi Bardia	

List of posters:

P01	Anand	Divya	Development of conducting nanocomposites by simultaneous in situ polymerization of aniline and matrix assembly from bacterial cellulose nanowhiskers
P02	Anjaneyulu	Oruganti	Pt/TiN Nanocomposite for Photothermal CO oxidation
P03	Bhargava	Priyanshu	Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) possesses anticancer activity: Molecular characterization and its enhancement with γ CD
P04	Chitrangi	Swati	Three Dimensional Polymer Scaffolds for Enhanced Differentiation of Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells to Hepatocyte-like Cells: A Comparative Study
P05	Dudani	Amrita	Synergistic action of motilin and ghrelin facilitates different responses in various parts of the Suncus stomach in vitro
P06	Dudekula	Althaf Basha	Application of STEM low angle annular dark field diffraction contrast to imaging of severely deformed alloys

P07	Fujita	N.	A Novel Long-Period Structure Formed in a High-Pressure Synthesized Mg-Zn-Yb Alloy
P08	Garg	Sukant	Cell-based screening of natural compounds for effective cancer treatment
P09	Garg	Sukant	Prosthesis Effective for Restoration of Fracture Enhanced with Cancer Treatment (Perfect) HIP
P10	Huda	Khateeb NOOR UI	Numerical Simulation of Bubbly Flows in an Aeration Tank with Biochemical Reactions
P11	Ji	Xin	Effect of graded β phase stability on deformation behavior in a metastable β -Ti alloy
P12	K	Dudhate Ambika	Functional analysis of defense related transcription factors in rice against sheath blight pathogen <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
P13	Kageyama	Daisuke	Profound Effects of Intracellular Microorganisms on Arthropod Reproduction and Development
P14	Kalra	Rajkumar S.	CARF determines the fate of cells through regulation of DNA damage and growth arrest signaling
P15	Kido	Shoichiro	Representation of Ningaloo Niño in the CMIP5 models
P16	Kulkarni	Manjiri	Structural Analysis of Sero-specific Immune Responses Using Epitope Grafted Mutants of Dengue Serotypes
P17	Kumar	Mukesh	Refractory Materials for Plasmonic Applications: a Theoretical Insight
P18	Li	Cheng-Lin	A Study On Deformation Behavior Of A Chemical Graded Beta Ti-10Mo-xFe Alloy
P19	Li	Kejuan	Anticancer activity in aqueous extract of <i>Helicteres angustifolia</i> L. root and its anticancer mechanisms
P21	Ling	Li	Mortalin regulates melanogenesis: evidence from cell culture based assays
P22	Manila	Nisha Gowri	IGF-I Receptor Influences Radiation-Induced G2 Arrest in HeLa Cells Expressing Fluorescent Ubiquitination-Based Cell Cycle Indicator (Fucci)
P23	Misra	Prakhar	Air Quality Analysis in Indian Cities Using Remote Sensing and Economic Growth Parameters
P24	Nigam	Nupur	Molecular mechanism of anticancer activity in Embelin, a quinone derivative of <i>Embelia ribes</i>
P25	Ohishi	Shun	Zonal movement of Mascarene High in austral summer

P26	Oono	Youko	Development of hexaploid wheat mutant populations through nontransgenic approach to the crop improvement
P27	Painumgal	Unnikrishnan V	Project Clean World: An attempt to achieve Zero Waste in India
P28	Payra	Debabrata	Facile and Rational Modulation of Ubiquitous Plant Polyphenols: Novel Multifunctional Coating Precursors from Nature
P29	Ping	D. H.	The hardening source of steel: ω -Fe
P30	Qiang	Jian	Effect of composition on property change in ZrCuAlNi metallic glasses after high-pressure torsion
P31	Ramaiah	Manish	Economic Analyses of Micro-irrigation in Four Water-scarce Areas in India
P32	Rathore	Himankshi	Automated 'PCR-on-paper' based point-of-care-testing of infectious diseases
P33	Richa	Tambi	Accelerated H-DROP: an SVM based helical domain linker predictor trained with features optimized by combining random forest and stepwise selection
P34	Subbaiah	Edupalli V.	Engineering Silkworms For Resistance To Baculovirus Through Multigene Therapy (RNA Interference)
P35	T	Jothi Saravanan	Environmental Impact Assessment for Infrastructure projects
P36	Takanashi	Naoto	Phase-contrast characteristics of ABF-STEM
P37	Tasaki	Wataru	Effect of Deformation Temperature on Low-Cycle Fatigue Properties in Fe-28Mn-6Si-5Cr Shape Memory Alloy
P38	Yamashita	Kenya	Structure refinements of the LPSO-Mg alloys based on STEM imaging combined with CBED
P39	Yasuike	Masato	Relation between Typhoon Characteristics and Climate Variations
P40	Yu	Yue	miR-335 induces apoptosis by targeting CARF in U2OS cells
P41	Zhou	Wenchong	First-principles study on phase stability in β -type Ti-X alloys (X = Mo, Al, Sn, Zr, Nb)

Keynote Lectures

KL01:

Frontier in Marine Science and Technology: The Role of JAMSTEC

Asahiko Taira

President, Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)

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JAMSTEC, after its establishment in 1971, has engaged in the promotion of marine-earth science and technology as one of the leading research institutes in the world. Especially noteworthy engineering achievements include the launch and operation of the deep-sea submersibles “Shinkai 6500”, the record-making supercomputer “Earth Simulator” and the deep-sea scientific drilling vessel “Chikyu”. The last twenty years have seen rapid expansion of our research capability, with accompanied strong publication records, in the study of climate change, dynamics of the Earth’s interior and the nature of extremophiles. On 11 March 2011, an unprecedented mega-earthquake and tsunami struck eastern Japan. Here I introduce some of the prominent results of a series of expeditions conducted by JAMSTEC and international group of researchers including IODP’s “Japan Trench Fast Drilling Project”.

Plenary Lectures

PL01:

Materials Technology for Safe and Secure Social Infrastructures

Koichi Tsuchiya^{1,2}

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In Japan, a large portion of social infrastructures, *e.g.*, bridges, tunnels, railways, *etc.*, were built during the time when Japanese economy was growing rapidly. Aging and degradation of these structures is one of the major social concerns. Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT) estimated that about 26% of the bridges (over 15 m) will be over 50 years old by 2020, and 53% by 2040. MLIT also warned that the cost for the maintenance and renewal for the infrastructure is about 0.8 billion JP¥ in 2010; this will be doubled by 2013.

In response to this crisis, it is urgent to develop various technologies: i) Technology to monitor the degradation of the infrastructures quantitatively. ii) Low cost repairing and reinforcement technology for the degraded infrastructures. iii) Development of the long-life, high strength materials. The present talk will introduce some of the materials technologies being developed in NIMS, which may offer some solutions to this urgent social issue.

PL02:

Efficient production of active form of vitamin D₃ by microbial conversion

Tomohiro TAMURA

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Vitamin D₃ (VD₃) is fat-soluble prohormone that plays a crucial role in bone metabolism, immunity and the control of cell proliferation and differentiation. The most active form, 1 α ,25(OH)₂VD₃, is used to treat osteoporosis, hyperparathyroidism, psoriasis, and VD₃ metabolic abnormality. The industrial production of 1 α ,25(OH)₂VD₃ is performed chemically or microbiologically, but the processes for the microbiological production of the active form of VD₃ are simpler than those for chemical synthesis. The actinomycete *Pseudonocardia autotrophica* is capable of bioconversion of VD₃ into its physiologically active forms, 25(OH)VD₃ or 1 α ,25(OH)₂VD₃. We identified vitamin D₃ hydroxylase (vdh) from *P. autotrophica* and characterized it structurally and enzymatically. Biotransformation of VD₃ into 25(OH)₂VD₃ was then accompanied with a Vdh-expressed recombinant strain of actinomycete *Rhodococcus erythropolis*. We have recently succeeded in significant improvement of cellular permeability of vitamin D₃ by using nisin-treated cells, and have developed a new platform for vitamin D₃ hydroxylation process.

In my talk, I would like to introduce how to improve the efficiency of production of hydroxylated form of vitamin D₃ by using *Rhodococcus erythropolis* as a host cells.

PL03:

A New Era of Electron Microscopy for Materials Science

Eiji Abe

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Precise characterizations of local element distributions as well as local atomic configurations are essential to understand the microscopic origins of materials' properties. Recent developments of aberration-correction electron optics have significantly advanced the microscope performance particularly of scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), enabling identification of individual atoms from low- to high-atomic-number elements – even the lightest hydrogen atoms can be successfully imaged by annular-bright-field (ABF) STEM [1]. I will describe some of our recent results that demonstrate the powerful use of the modern STEM for characterizations of complex-structured materials, including LPSO-Mg alloys [2] and quasicrystals [3].

References

1. R. Ishikawa, E. Okunishi, H. Sawada, Y. Kondo, F. Hosokawa and E. Abe “Direct imaging of hydrogen-atom columns in a crystal by annular bright-field electron microscopy” *Nature Materials*, 10, 278 (2011).
2. D. Egusa and E. Abe “The structure of long period stacking/order Mg–Zn–RE phases with extended non-stoichiometry ranges” *Acta Materialia* 60, 166 (2012).
3. E. Abe “Electron microscopy of quasicrystals – *where are the atoms?*” *Chem Soc Rev* 41, 6787 (2012).

Invited Lectures

IL01:

Status of Delhi Light Source Project (DLS) with R&D at KEK

Junji Urakawa

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The demand for the photon beams with high brightness and short pulse length is growing in India. To address the requirements, a project to develop a compact Light Source based on the principle of Free Electron Laser at Inter University Accelerator Centre (IUAC) has been initiated and it was named as Delhi Light Source (DLS). In the first phase of the project, prebunched electron beam of energy 7 - 8 MeV will be produced by a normal conducting photocathode RF gun and coherent THz radiation will be produced by injecting the electron beam into a compact undulator magnet. To make the facility compact, less expensive and simple, a method to generate the 'comb beam' structure of electron beam has been adopted. By changing the separation between the successive electron microbunches at the photocathode, the tuning of the THz will be accomplished. The progress of the first phase of DLS will be explained in this talk. Also, since Indian accelerator researchers are going to learn necessary accelerator science and technology at KEK, I will present the status of R&D for DLS project, especially manufacturing process of RF gun cavity and the simulation results carried out using ASTRA code for optimization of various parameters from photocathode RF gun up to the undulator magnet instead of them.

Lectures

L01:

Nondestructive study of Japanese iron artifacts using pulsed neutron imaging for evaluating crystallographic texture and microstructure

Manako Tanaka¹, Yoshinori Shiota², Yoshiaki Kiyonagi²

¹Tokyo University of the Arts, ²Nagoya University

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It is said that traditional Japanese iron has good workability and does not rust easily. The reasons of these characteristics are derived from the raw materials, iron making technique and iron manufacturing technique in ancient Japan. However, the details of these techniques are not clear as they were mainly carried out in secret. We have started a nondestructive study of iron artifacts using the advanced analytical instruments such as synchrotron radiation and neutron¹. The purpose of this work is to evaluate crystallographic texture and microstructure of two specimen of a traditional Japanese matchlock gun by pulsed neutron imaging and to compare them with the information obtained by optical microscopic observation. The experiment was carried out by pulsed neutron imaging using the TOF method (Fig.1) at J-PARC/MLF.

Fig.1 Experimental layout

Each sample showed a distinctive shape of the Bragg edge, which provides information on the crystallite size and degree of anisotropy. On the basis of the Rietveld-type analysis code², it became clear that the crystallite size in the breech is smaller than that of the muzzle and the preferred orientation of the breech is more isotropic than that in the muzzle. These results agreed very well with the results of optical microscopic observation. It is concluded that the pulsed neutron imaging technique will provide useful information for elucidating the manufacturing techniques of the Japanese iron artifacts non-destructively. We plan to use the results as basic data and to extend our study towards a systematic non-destructive measurement of iron artifacts.

References

1. M. Tanaka: *Hamon*, 25-1, pp. 8-12 (2015).
2. Y. Kiyonagi, H Sato, T. Kamiyama and T. Shinohara: *Journal of Physics, Conference Series* 340, 01 2010 (2012).

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI (No. 26702004 and No. 23226018), a grant from Iketani Science and Technology Foundation, and a grant from the Iron and Steel Institute of Japan.

L02:

Impact of the Moisture Variability on the Indian Summer Monsoon Rainfall

Satyaban B. Ratna^{1@}, Annalisa Cherchi^{2,3}, P. V. Joseph⁴, S. K. Behera¹, Abish. B. ⁴, Simona Masina^{2,3}

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In this study, we investigated how the decrease trend of moisture over the East Africa/Arabian Sea is related to the Indo-Pacific Ocean warming and how this could affect the variability of the Indian summer monsoon rainfall. We have analysed the observed precipitation, sea surface temperature and atmospheric reanalysis products from different datasets for the period 1951-2012. The results indicated that the decreasing trend of moisture over the East Africa/Arabian Sea coincides with an increasing trend of moisture over the western Pacific region. This is accompanied by the strengthening (weakening) of the upward motion over the western Pacific (East Africa/Arabian Sea) that, consequently, contributes to modulate the western Pacific-Indian Ocean Walker circulation. Enhanced convection and associated SST warming trend in the western Pacific are mostly responsible for the intensified rising motion. Linear trend of moisture convergence is weakening over the Indian landmass and contributing to the precipitation decrease. The low-level westerlies are weakening over the peninsular India, thus minimizes moisture transport towards India and reducing the associated rainfall.

L03:**First principles based phase field crystal model**Swastibrata Bhattacharyya¹, Kaoru Ohno¹, Ryoji Sahara^{2,3}¹Department of Physics, Yokohama National University, 79-5 Tokiwadai, Yokohama 240-8501, Japan,²National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), 1-2-1 Sengen, Tsukuba 305-0047, Japan,³Max-Planck-Institut für Eisenforschung Max-Planck-Straße 1, D-40237 Düsseldorf, Germany

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Understanding microstructures, formed during various processing conditions of materials, such as solidification, precipitation and heat treatment, is very important in predicting their durability and performance in different applications. These microstructures play an important role in determining many material properties such as strength, ductility, hardness, corrosion resistance, and temperature behavior to name a few. First principles methods such as density functional theory (DFT)[1, 2] cannot be used to study such phenomena due to the limitation of the maximum number of atoms it can deal with. Phase field model (PFM) [3] offers a powerful tool to study evolution of microstructures and phase transformations theoretically. PFM has been successful in producing microstructural patterns and their dynamics in various alloys and mixtures. Phase field crystal (PFC) model [4, 5], a modified methodology has also been developed to study the growth of crystals by including a periodic field into the standard PFM. However, PFM is a purely empirical approach and requires thermodynamic inputs that are difficult to measure. There is no direct connection between this model and the first principles methods. Hence PFM is not been widely accepted in various industries. The purpose of our study is to bridge these two different methods and to derive the phase field model from the viewpoint of the first principles theory. Using this derived equation we studied the growth of a crystal from nuclei in a liquid. Furthermore, in this approach we have included the effect of temperature. Although this is not a unique way to map onto the PFC model, we present a possible approach to connect the first principles and the PFC model.

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5. Elder K. R. and Grant M. Phys. Rev. E 70, 051605 (2004)

L04:**Self-assembly of siRNA Embedded Protein for ‘Artificial Viruses’**

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Artificial viruses can be used as model systems for providing insights into natural viruses that is considered as one of the efficient vectors for gene delivery and can be manipulated based on intelligent design. GroEL is a cylindrical protein with structural stability that allows mutation and chemical modifications while maintaining its shape. Previously we have found that selective mutation in apical domain of GroEL can self-assemble to make protein fiber when divalent cation is added¹. Here we present another surprising self-assembly of engineered-GroEL triggered by a surface treated siRNA (siRNA-nanocaplet) without any metal ions. The siRNA-nanocaplet consists of a polymer composed of disulfide bonds in the backbone, which form by siRNA-templated polymerization of a guanidine monomer bearing two thiols². The monodisperse complexes of polymer and siRNA fit into the hydrophobic cavity of GroEL proteins, triggering a supramolecular assembly to form a tubular nanocarrier. The siRNA-nanocaplet payload can be released by the combined actions of intracellular adenosine-5'-triphosphate (ATP) and glutathione (GSH). We believe this responsive virus-like carrier efficiently takes cargo siRNA into the cell and knock down the protein expression *in vivo*.

Figure 1. Illustration of siRNA-embedded GroEL protein self-assembly and guest release

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L05:

Microbial Biofilms and Medical Devices

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Adhesion to a substrate or interphase and colonizing to form biofilms is a survival tactic of microorganisms. This behavior has been both a boon and a curse to man. It's been a boon when we have developed energy efficient ways of waste water treatment, metal ore purification, cheese making etc. But it's been a curse when medical devices have been implanted in patients to address severe and debilitating conditions. Medical device usage has led to the development of medical device related infections, which are recalcitrant to antibiotic treatment and in severe cases requiring removal of the device.

Three factors are responsible for development of medical device related infections: microbial factors, host factors and device factors. Of these the device factors are the most amenable to modification and continuous research in the area has led to many technological advances. Surface modifications include Silver or silver oxide coating, hydrogel coating, controlled drugs like antibiotic eluting surfaces, diamond-like carbon coating, anti-adhesivepeptide coatings etc the list being endless. But yet the problem persists, throwing up challenges to researchers and medical practitioners alike. Consequences of implant associated infections include prolonged systemic antibiotic therapy, several revision procedures, prolonged hospitalization and in some cases removal of the implant. We as a community have to address the issue if we have to ensure that the true benefits of medical devices and technological advances in health- care reach the needy.

Poster
Presentations

P01:

Development of conducting nanocomposites by simultaneous *in situ* polymerization of aniline and matrix assembly from bacterial cellulose nanowhiskers

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Development of new greener material for conducting paper is sought for applications such as security paper, actuators, and anti-static packaging. It is required that the material for these applications possess low density and good mechanical integrity. This work presents a way to produce bacterial nanocellulose (BC) - polyaniline (PANI) nanocomposites by *in situ* polymerization in suspension of cellulose nanowhiskers. The advantages of using BC over filter paper are its ultrafine network structure, sufficient porosity, high purity and crystallinity, good mechanical properties, great water holding capability and low environmental impact. The BC/PANI composites formed by optimized synthesis of PANI within cellulose nanowhiskers are expected to possess good electrical conductivity in addition to excellent mechanical properties and flexibility. The material has been characterized using FTIR, SEM and 4-probe conductivity measurement equipment.

P02

Pt/TiN Nanocomposite for Photothermal CO oxidation

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Titanium nitride (TiN) is unique due to its excellent physical, chemical properties and biocompatibility.¹ Low cost, high thermal stability, broad band absorption and local heating efficiency makes TiN as a novel plasmonic material for catalytic applications.^{2,3}

Plasmon mediated photo thermal catalysis is of confocal interest to reduce the fuel consumption in high temperature catalysis but has been relying on expensive and earth-scarce gold (Au) materials. Here we report utilizing a low cost and abundant material like titanium nitride (TiN) with wide range visible light absorption ability as an alternative plasmonic material to promote oxidation of carbon dioxide ($\text{CO} + 1/2\text{O}_2 = \text{CO}_2$) by photo thermal means. Nanocubes (NCs, 50nm) TiN prepared by thermal plasma method (TPM) were decorated with platinum nanoparticles (NPs, 10nm) via borohydride reduction route to yield TiN- supported Pt catalysts (Pt/TiN). Under the illumination of solar simulator light (Wavelength: 300-1100 nm) Pt/TiN catalyst promotes CO oxidation while SiO₂ supported Pt remains intact. Electromagnetic simulations elucidated that the enhanced light driven CO oxidation over Pt/TiN is attributed to the ability of TiN NCs converting light to heat through enhanced excitation of surface plasmons.

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P03:

**Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) possesses anticancer activity:
Molecular characterization and its enhancement with γ CD**

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Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) is a major ingredient in New Zealand propolis. It is known for a variety of health promoting and therapeutic potentials. We investigated the molecular mechanism of anticancer and anti-metastasis activities of CAPE. cDNA array analysis of the control and CAPE-treated human breast cancer cells revealed upregulation of GADD45 α and p53 tumor suppressor proteins. We found that CAPE caused disruption of mortalin-p53 complexes and led to nuclear translocation and activation of p53 resulting in growth arrest in cancer cells. CAPE-treated cells exhibited down regulation of mortalin and several other key regulators of cell migration accountable for its anti-metastasis activity. Of note, we found that whereas CAPE was unstable in the culture medium (as it gets degraded into caffeic acid by secreted esterases), its complex with γ CD showed high efficacy in anti-tumor and anti-metastasis assays *in vitro* and *in vivo* (when administered through either intraperitoneal or oral route). The data proposes that CAPE- γ CD complex is a potent anti-cancer and anti-metastasis reagent.

P04:

Three Dimensional Polymer Scaffolds for Enhanced Differentiation of Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells to Hepatocyte-like Cells: A Comparative Study

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Stem cell-based tissue engineering has emerged as a promising avenue for treatment of liver diseases and as drug metabolism and toxicity models in drug discovery and development. *In vitro* simulation of microenvironment niche for hepatic differentiation remains elusive, due to lack of information about crucial factors for the stem cell niche. For generation of functional hepatocytes, an *in vivo* three-dimensional (3D) microenvironment and architecture should be reproduced. Towards this, we fabricated three scaffolds as DG1 (Dextran-Gelatin), CH1 (Chitosan-Hyaluronic acid) and GEVAC (Gelatin-Vinyl Acetate). Hepatic differentiation of human umbilical cord derived mesenchymal stem cells (hUC-MSCs) was induced by culturing hUC-MSCs on these scaffolds. The scaffolds support hepatic differentiation by mimicking the native extracellular matrix (ECM) microenvironment and architecture to facilitate 3D cell-cell and cell-matrix interactions. The expression of hepatic markers, glycogen storage, urea production, albumin secretion and cytochrome P450 (CYP450) activity induced hepatic differentiation of hUC-MSCs. The differentiated hUC-MSCs on the 3D scaffolds formed hepatospheroids (three dimensional hepatocyte aggregate) as illustrated by scanning electron microscopy, immunofluorescent staining and cytoskeleton organization. It was observed that the 3D scaffolds supported improved cell morphology, expression of hepatic markers and metabolic activities as compared to matrigel coated plates. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report demonstrating the use of well-characterized scaffold (GEVAC) for enhanced differentiation of hUC-MSCs to hepatocyte-like cells (HLCs).

P05:

Synergistic action of motilin and ghrelin facilitates different responses in various parts of the Suncus stomach in vitro

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Co-ordination of motilin and ghrelin is necessary for the initiation of phase III contractions. We have previously observed that motilin and ghrelin induce Suncus gastric contraction in vitro and in vivo. Therefore, we hypothesized that certain regions in the stomach must be more responsive to motilin and ghrelin, and that strong gastric contractions are propagated from that site. From the in vitro contractile study, we found that motilin and ghrelin-induced contractions differed in different parts of the stomach, and they are mediated by the cholinergic neural pathway in the myenteric plexus. Only the fundus and upper corpus induced gastric contractions with 10^{-9} M-motilin treatment. GPR38 mRNA expression was higher in the upper corpus than other segments. Also, the ghrelin cell density and GHSR mRNA expression was higher in the fundus and upper corpus than in other parts. These results suggest that the upper corpus may be the most sensitive and responsive to motilin- and ghrelin-induced synergistic gastric contractions.

P06:

Application of STEM low angle annular dark field diffraction contrast to imaging of severely deformed alloys

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Microstructural investigation of extremely strained samples using the conventional TEM techniques is very challenging due to strong image contrast resulting from the high defect density. Application of low angle annular dark field (LAADF) mode in STEM mode to study crystal defects and recrystallization phenomenon in severely deformed samples provide the fundamental insights into their deformation behavior. LAADF-STEM images can be obtained by collecting Bragg diffracted electrons from an appropriate angle. The present contribution highlights LAADF imaging advantages for observation of twinning, grain fragmentation, nucleation of recrystallized grains and precipitates on second phase particles in highly strained regions of metallic specimens. LAADF imaging also enables to observe the clear grain boundary with a sharp diffraction contrast by minimizing all strain effects which facilitates to measure the accurate grain size in deformation processed specimens.

P07:

A Novel Long-Period Structure Formed in a High-Pressure Synthesized Mg-Zn-Yb Alloy

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Long-period stacking/ordered (LPSO) structures are formed in a number of Mg-TM-RE (TM: transition metal, RE: rare earth) alloys. Empirically, it is known that there is a preferential for RE atoms; i.e., RE must be trivalent [1]. Generally, Yb is divalent under an ordinary pressure, but it could be trivalent under high-pressure conditions. With this in mind, Matsushita et al. attempted a high-pressure synthesis of Mg-Zn-Yb alloys, and found formation of the LPSO-like phase that shows the diffraction patterns similar to those observed in LPSO-forming Mg-Zn-Y alloys. In the present work, we aimed to determine its structure based on atomic-resolution HAADF/ABF-STEM imaging combined with first-principles calculations.

Mg₉₇Zn₁Yb₂ alloy was quenched in water after annealing at 673K, under 5GPa for 30minutes. Specimens for TEM/STEM were cut from the quenched-ingot, and then thinned by mechanical polishing, and finally by ion-milling. Figure1 shows HAADF-STEM images of the high-pressure synthesized Mg₉₇Zn₁Yb₂ alloy, taken with the incident beam parallel to the $[\bar{1}10]$ (a), and $[110]$ (b) direction of the Mg-matrix. It is noticed that there occurs a clear six-intensity modulation along the *c*-axis, relevant long-period order is evidently different from the previous structures. We will construct a model structure with the aid of image simulations and first-principle calculations.

period
and the
LPSO

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Fig.1 HAADF-STEM images of the high-pressure synthesized Mg₉₇Zn₁Yb₂ alloy, taken with the incident beam parallel to the $[\bar{1}10]$ (a), and $[110]$ (b) direction of the Mg-matrix.

P08:

Cell-based screening of natural compounds for effective cancer treatment

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Cancer is a complex disease, most consistently defined as uncontrolled and indefinite proliferation of cells. Caused by multitude of genetic and environmental factors, it has only a limited treatment success. Customary treatments include surgery, radio- and chemotherapies involving removal or killing of cancer cells, respectively. Several studies have indicated that stress is tightly connected to carcinogenesis. Cancer represents a highly stressed physiological state in which the cells escape the stress-signaling mediated growth arrest. Our group has earlier identified anti-cancer activity in leaves of Ashwagandha and has defined some mechanisms involved in selective killing of cancer cells¹. The active phytochemicals from Ashwagandha leaves (withanolides) caused oxidative stress to cancer cells². At the same time, they were shown to protect normal cells against a variety of stresses³⁻⁸.

In view of the above findings, we screened some natural purified for anti-stress and anti-cancer potentials. We anticipated that in addition to their value for cancer therapy, these might also possess cancer-preventive potentials. The later constitutes a highly prioritized field of research in the current scenario of (i) increasing levels of stress due to high use of chemicals in our daily living and (ii) increasing old age societies worldwide. We undertook a screening of small library of natural compounds using cell based stress survival assays. Oxidative stress to human normal fibroblasts (TIG-3) and osteosarcoma cells (U2OS) was imparted by their direct exposure to hydrogen peroxide or UV at doses that caused about 40% reduction in their viability as measured by MTT-based cell viability assay. Cells were allowed to recover either in the normal cell culture medium or in presence of a variety of natural compounds. We have identified candidate compounds that showed enhanced cytotoxicity to cancer cells. We used low doses of these compounds in stress-survival assays and identified several compounds that that caused sensitization of cancer cells to oxidative stress. We propose that these may serve as useful adjuvants in cancer treatment.

P09:

Prosthesis Effective for Restoration of Fracture Enhanced with Cancer Treatment (Perfect) HIP

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Hip joint, as the weight bearing joint is subjected to a variety of stresses. Prone to complicated fractures as a result of and in synergy with diseases like cancer, it now accounts for nearly a million new cases worldwide yearly. Various attempts have been made to understand and simulate natural hip dynamics with artificial materials. However, most hip prosthesis currently utilized in an orthopedic clinic have limitations e.g., infection, damage to neighboring structures, post-surgical rejection, etc. To address this condition, we tried to develop the design of an artificial hip prosthesis.

After a detailed market analysis, conceptualization, materials study, competitive benchmarking and CAD designs, we have developed the design of *Perfect HIP*, the prosthetic device with superior geometry, reduced von Mises stresses and corrosion speed, and self-antibiotic potential, further verified by finite element analysis. We hope to amplify the potential of the prosthesis by enveloping its surface with biocompatible and sustained release cancer preventive phytochemicals to prevent prosthetic induced carcinogenic mutations and to aid the hip fractures complicated due to cancer radiation therapy. We believe that the design would not only address the need of the patient in desperate medical conditions, but also improve their quality of life, with respect to health and cost, co-arising from orthopedic and oncology OPDs.

¹ Deceased

P10:**Numerical Simulation of Bubbly Flows in an Aeration Tank with Biochemical Reactions**

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The primary purpose is incorporation of all the biochemical reactions numerically in the aeration tank to create a model representing reactor of wastewater treatment using the bubble plume system as the reaction tank. This study is an application of Murai and Matsumoto [1] and Gong et al [2].

There are two main types of biological reactions, Aerobic and Anaerobic. Several substrates are consumed by bacteria and simultaneous growth of bacteria. Reaction is written as combination of three half-reactions, electron donor reaction, electron acceptor reaction and cell synthesis reaction [3, 4]. Reactions mainly follow Monod kinetics with an exception of a few following first order kinetics. Regrowth is based on a model by Dold et al. [5] where bacteria is continually undergoing death and lysis, yielding substrate (used again by bacteria's as food) and debris.

Governing equations: Combination of continuity equation and species conservation equation. (Liquid phase). Finite Volume Method is used for discretization and first order upwind interpolation scheme is used. Validation is carried out using the study, Mohan, S. Venkata, et al [6]. The results from the study and model is compared. Value of slopes from study and model is 1.96×10^{-6} kg/m³/s and 1.89×10^{-6} kg/m³/s. Error between the slopes was about 3.5%. The validation was carried out for aerobic and anaerobic reactions separately as. All the errors were within the considered range.

A detailed model for biological wastewater purification involving several biochemical reactions using bacteria's is developed in the bubble plume as the base.

P11:**Effect of graded β phase stability on deformation behavior
in a metastable β -Ti alloy**Xin JI^{1,2}, Ivan Gutierrez-Urrutia², Satoshi EMURA², Koichi TSUCHIYA^{1,2}¹University of Tsukuba, Japan, ²National Institute for Materials Science, Japan
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Metastable β -Ti alloys typically deform by slip, twinning, martensitic transformation as well as by the combination of them. The deformation mode is closely related to the β phase stability which is a function of chemical composition. The purpose of this study is to investigate the deformation behaviors in the metastable β -Ti alloy with graded β phase stability, which is prompted by elemental segregation. Ti-12Mo (mass %) alloy with segregation was used for the study. In the sample the content of Mo element ranged from less than 10% to higher than 13%. Deformation was applied by interrupted tensile tests at a constant strain rate of $2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Through the microstructural characterization of the deformed specimen with 4.7% strain, the coexistence of various deformation modes, i.e. dislocation slip, $\{332\}$ $\langle 113 \rangle$ twinning and stress-induced α'' martensite was confirmed. Meanwhile the change from twin-to-martensite transformation was observed within a single deformation band structure. Combined with EPMA results, it was realized that the α'' martensite plates exist in the Mo lean region while the twins exist in the Mo-rich region. It can be inferred that the β phase stability governs the critical stress for the formation of stress-induced martensite and twinning.

P12:

Functional analysis of defense related transcription factors in rice against sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Phytochrome and *Flowering Time 1 (PFT1)* gene is identified as mediator complex with disease resistance as one of the many functional roles in *Arabidopsis*. *Arabidopsis* MYC2 gene is a negative transcription factor known to be involved in down regulating defense related genes; hence, silencing it helps in the up regulation of defense genes. An attempt was made to study the function role of the above two homologues genes (*OsPFT1* and *OsMYC*) in rice against sheath blight pathogen, ***Rhizoctonia solani***. To test the role of *OsPFT1* gene in rice, *pUbi:OsPFT1* gene construct was mobilized into *Agrobacterium* strain LBA4404 by triparental mating method. The presence of the binary vector in the *Agrobacterium* strain was confirmed by back transformation into *E. coli* and further confirmed by PCR and restriction enzyme analysis. Sheath blight susceptible *indica* rice cultivar, ASD16 was used for *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation of *pUbi:OsPFT1* construct. Several rounds of co-cultivation resulted in the generation of 16 putative transgenic plants of three independent events. PCR analysis for *hpt* gene and *OsPFT1* gene showed that all the 16 plants contained the transgene. Screening for sheath blight disease showed enhanced level of resistance in two out of the three transgenic events.

In order to silence the MYC gene of rice, *pStargate:OsMYC* gene construct was used for *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation of *indica* rice, ASD16. Several rounds of co-cultivation resulted in the generation of 21 putative transgenic plants of single event. PCR analysis done on 10 T₁ transgenic plants showed the presence of the *hpt* gene and *OCS* terminator. Bioassay done for sheath blight disease showed enhanced level of resistance in transgenic plants silenced for *OsMYC* gene compared to ASD16 control plants.

Keywords: MYC, Sheath blight, *Rhizoctonia Solani*, *Agrobacterium*

P13:

Profound Effects of Intracellular Microorganisms on Arthropod Reproduction and Development

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Increasing attention has been paid to the microorganisms that are capable of living only in the cells of arthropods. Considering the fact that our planet is dominated by arthropods – which comprise more than 80% of all the described living animals and live in all the ecosystems (such as marine, freshwater, land and even air) – intracellular environment of arthropods can be regarded as a large and important biosphere for some microorganisms.

Because such microorganisms cannot live outside of the host cells and the host arthropods are mortal (i.e., having limited life span), the only means for them to survive is to be transmitted to subsequent generations of the hosts. Although females produce large ovaries which have sufficient room for microorganisms, sperms produced by males do not have any room for the microorganisms. Namely, transmission to subsequent host generations are possible only through females – males are dead-end. Because of this asymmetry (i.e., 50% loss), some microorganisms have evolved a variety of tactic strategies to enhance their own transmission to subsequent generations. I am going to show how deeply such microorganisms interact with the fundamental biological system of arthropods from the viewpoint of developmental and evolutionary biology.

P14:

CARF determines the fate of cells through regulation of DNA damage and growth arrest signaling

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CARF (Collaborator of ARF) is an ARF-interacting protein that also binds to and regulates HDM2 and p53 proteins. It was earlier shown that CARF upregulates ARF-p53-p21 tumor suppressor axis resulting in growth arrest in cancer cells. Consistent to this functionality of CARF, it was upregulated in cells undergoing a variety of stresses and replicative senescence. It was shown to be an essential protein; CARF compromised cells undergo apoptosis. Furthermore, level of CARF expression determined fate of cells to growth arrest or malignant transformation by fine-tuning of DNA damage response involving damage-signaling and -responding proteins. We found that super-high level of expression of CARF resulted in negative regulation of p53, driven by HDM2 feedback circuit and transcriptional upregulation of CHK2. These resulted in abrogation of CARF induced growth arrest and induced malignant transformation. In line with this, p53 deficient cells were found to escape CARF-induced growth arrest, and instead showed increase in malignant characteristics that was mediated by transcriptional repression of p21^{W^{WP}}, a critical mediator of growth arrest. Taken together, it is discovered that CARF determines fate of cells by two-way regulation of DNA damage and growth arrest signaling.

P15:

Representation of Ningaloo Niño in the CMIP5 models

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Ningaloo Niño, which is a recently identified climate mode, has strong impacts on marine ecosystems off the west coast of Australia and precipitation over there. In this study, we examine the ability of the state-of-the-art climate models to simulate this climate mode using outputs from 17 models that participated in the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project, phase 5 (CMIP5). It turns out that 8 out of 17 models reproduce sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies associated with Ningaloo Niño/Niña successfully, but the location of peak SST anomalies is very different from the observation in 2 models. Also, fundamental features such as the seasonality and associated anomalous atmospheric circulation and precipitation are fairly well reproduced in most models, but the amplitude varies significantly among the models. We find that the inter-model differences in the amplitude are mainly caused by that in the magnitude of remote influences from the El Niño-Southern Oscillation via oceanic and atmospheric teleconnections. On the other hand, the strength of local air-sea interaction does not contribute much to the inter-model difference. This study suggests some possible remedies for an improved simulation of Ningaloo Niño in CGCMs.

P16:

Structural Analysis of Sero-specific Immune Responses Using Epitope Grafted Mutants of Dengue Serotypes

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Dengue is currently a major global health problem. Development of an effective tetravalent dengue vaccine is a need of time. The uniqueness of the dengue viruses (DENVs) and the severe spectrum of disease resulting from secondary infection of different serotype(s) have made dengue vaccine development difficult. The third domain of the viral envelope protein (ED3) contains the two major putative epitopes and is a highly suitable model protein for examining the molecular determinants of a virus' sero-specificity. In this study, we examine the sero-specificity and cross reactivity of the immune response against DEN3 and DEN4 ED3 using six epitope grafted ED3 variants where the surface-exposed epitope residues from DEN3 ED3 were switched to those of DEN4 ED3 and *vice versa*. We prepared anti-DEN3 and anti-DEN4 ED3 serum by immunizing Swiss Albino mice and measured their reactivities against all six grafted mutants. As expected, both sera exhibited strong reactivity against its own serotype's ED3, and little cross-reactivity against their counterpart serotype's ED3s. We observed amino acid residues from putative epitope 2 (E2) plays a major role in the sero-specificity of anti-DEN3 serum, whereas epitope 1 (E1) was important for DEN4 ED3's sero-specificity. To analyze the above results from a structural viewpoint, we determined the crystal structure of a DEN4 ED3 variant, where E2 was grafted from DEN3 ED3, at 2.78Å resolution and modeled the structures of the five remaining grafted variants by assuming that the overall backbone remained unchanged. The examination of the electrostatic and molecular surfaces of the variants suggested some further rationale for the sero-specificity of the immune responses. This study will explore the foundation for design of the vaccine against dengue.

Protein Data bank ID for the crystal structure of the DEN4 mutant (DEN4_E2^{DEN3}): **4X42**.

Reference:

Kulkarni, M.R., et al., Structural and biophysical analysis of sero-specific immune responses using epitope grafted Dengue ED3 mutants. *Biochimica et Biophysica acta*, 2015. 1854: 1438-43.

P17:

Refractory Materials for Plasmonic Applications: a Theoretical Insight

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Plasmonics has opened the door for many technological applications such as bio-sensing, solar energy harvesting, optical metamaterials, and subwavelength communication devices in the last few decades [1]. However, the absence of robust, high performance, high temperature stable, and low cost plasmonic materials that can be easily integrated into already established technologies, are some of the challenges. In this context, present study provides a detailed discussion on refractory conductive ceramics as alternative plasmonic materials. The electronic, optical and plasmonic properties of various conductive ceramics such as TiC, ZrC, HfC, TaC, WC, TiN, ZrN, HfN, TaN and WN are studied systematically by means of the both first-principles density functional theory and electromagnetic simulation. Plasma frequency, scattering rate and optical properties such as dielectric functions, loss function, and reflectivity, are calculated including electronic interband and intraband transitions. The scattering and absorption efficiencies of refractory nanoparticles are evaluated.

Our calculations confirmed that transition metal nitrides such as TiN, ZrN and HfN are the strongest candidates (Fig.1) close to the performance of conventional noble metals in the visible to the near-infrared regions [2, 3]. TiN was found to be the best material for broadband photothermal application, even better than Au or Ag, whereas ZrN and HfN are found to be the candidates for low-loss and thus narrow-band plasmonic applications in the visible region.

Fig.1 Alternative refractory plasmonic materials

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P18:**A Study On Deformation Behavior Of A Chemical Graded Beta Ti-10Mo-xFe Alloy**Cheng-Lin Li¹, Ivan Gutierrez-Urrutia¹, Satoshi Emura¹, Koichi Tsuchiya¹¹National Institute for Materials Science, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-0047, Japan

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A study on deformation behavior of a multilayered material consisting of Ti-10Mo-1Fe and Ti-10Mo-3Fe (wt.%) was carried out using electron channeling contrast imaging (ECCI) and high resolution electron backscatter diffraction (HR-EBSD). We found that, a ~ 130 μm thick chemical graded structure with Fe content from 1 wt.% to 3 wt.% was formed between layers as a result of heat diffusion during thermomechanical processing. The deformation mode in the chemical graded structure depended strongly on the Fe content, namely, single slips occurred in the Fe-rich bands (>2.0 wt.%) and {332}<113> deformation twins occurred in the Fe-lean bands (1~1.8 wt.%) to accommodate the macroscopic stress. In addition, an orientation gradient band was formed at the terminated twin tips (Fe content 1.8~2.0 wt.%) to accommodate the local stress. The terminated primary twins also stimulated a series of secondary {332}<113> twins with a few micrometers, alternately with a/2<111> type dislocations at the twin tip (orientation gradient band). The deformation modes of the single slip and {332}<113> twinning followed the Schmid law. Deformation twins nucleated at grain boundaries where the Fe content was about 1.2 wt.%, and stopped in the grain interior where the Fe content was about 1.8 wt.%. There was no any sharp interface where the twins have stopped. We claimed that the Fe content played a key role in the twin propagation due to a sharp increase in twinning stress (637 MPa for Ti-10Mo-1Fe to 864 MPa for Ti-10Mo-2Fe).

P19:

Anticancer activity in aqueous extract of *Helicteres angustifolia* L. root and its anticancer mechanisms

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Helicteres angustifolia L. (*H. angustifolia*) is a common shrub that widely used in Traditional Chinese Medicine system to prevent/treat cancer. In order to provide more evidence on the anticancer activity of *H. angustifolia* root, we prepared aqueous extract of *Helicteres angustifolia* L. roots (AQHAR) and performed several *in vitro* assays using human normal fibroblasts (TIG-3) and osteosarcoma (U2OS). We found that the AQHAR caused growth arrest/apoptosis of U2OS cells in a dose-dependent manner, while it showed no cytotoxicity to TIG-3 cells. Molecular analysis revealed upregulation of p53, p21 and downregulation of cyclin B1 and pRb in AQHAR treated U2OS cells. Moreover, biochemical analyses revealed that it induced ROS signaling and DNA damage response selectively in cancer cells. Furthermore, *in vivo* xenograft tumor assays in nude mice revealed dose-dependent suppression of tumor growth and lung metastasis with no toxicity to the animals suggesting the *H. angustifolia* may be a potent and safe natural resource for cancer treatment.

P20:

Mortalin regulates melanogenesis: evidence from cell culture based assays

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The process of melanogenesis in specialized skin cells, melanocytes, in the basal layer of epidermis produce melanin pigment and determines skin color from fair to dark. It has relevance not only in cosmetics but also several other characteristics of skin including its tolerance to stress and environmental conditions. Compared to white skin, dark skin has tolerance to high temperature, UV and oxidative stress. Several natural drugs from traditional home medicine have been shown to manipulate stress tolerance of skin. On the other hand, agents that induce depigmentation are valuable for treatment of dark spots (moles) that appear with aging.

In order to identify the cellular factors involved in human melanogenesis, we used shRNA-mediated loss-of-function screening in conjunction with induction of melanogenesis by OAG (diacylglycerol 1-oleoyl-2-acetyl-sn-glycerol) in human melanoma G361 cells. Cells were transfected with shRNA library and assayed for induction of melanogenesis by multidimensional approach, involving quantitative biochemical and visual determination of the melanin content and tyrosinase activity. Gene targets of the shRNAs that led to the loss of OAG-induced melanogenesis were considered as candidate cellular factors crucial for melanogenesis. By the four rounds of screenings, we identified several gene targets. Bioinformatics and pathway analyses revealed that these gene targets are involved in the regulation of cell proliferation, apoptosis, stress response and mitochondrial functions. Based on these data, the role of mitochondrial stress chaperone, mortalin in melanogenesis was discovered. We demonstrate (i) its use as a molecular target for manipulation of melanogenesis and (ii) whitening effect of Ashwagandha (a popular Ayurvedic herb) leaf extracts in OAG-induced melanogenesis in melanoma and melanocyte models suggesting its value for cosmetics and therapeutic manipulation of skin color and other characteristics regulating stress tolerance and pathologies.

P21:

IGF-I Receptor Influences Radiation-Induced G2 Arrest in HeLa Cells Expressing Fluorescent Ubiquitination-Based Cell Cycle Indicator (Fucci)

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When tumor cells deficient in the p53 function are irradiated, cells accumulate at G2/M boundary in cell cycle, which is a radiosensitive phase. This timing thus could provide a good opportunity to obtain an efficient cell killing effect for the next round of irradiation in a fractionated irradiation regimen. Usually, this has been studied using flow cytometric analysis; however, the methodology results in loss of temporospatial information. To overcome this issue, we introduced the fluorescent ubiquitination-based cell cycle indicator (Fucci) system, which visualizes cell cycle by emitting red and green fluorescence in G1 and S/G2/M phases, respectively. We previously reported that irradiated HeLa-Fucci cells exhibit accumulation of green phase cells, and subsequently red phase cells emerge, which perfectly reflects the G2 arrest kinetics. Taking advantage of this system, we explored the possible factors influencing the phenomenon. Insulin-like growth factor I receptor (IGF-IR) is a multifunctional tyrosine kinase receptor, including cell growth, transformation, inhibition of apoptosis, and DNA repair. A specific inhibitor for IGF-IR (NVP-AEW541) was used to abrogate the function of the receptor. It was confirmed that the inhibitor completely inhibits IGF-I-induced activation of ERK, a downstream kinase of IGF-IR, at a concentration of 2 μ M. The inhibitor did not significantly affect the normal cell cycle progression. Interestingly, appearance of red phase cells after green phase cell accumulation following 10 Gy irradiation was remarkably delayed when the inhibitor was combined. These results indicate that IGF-IR regulates the duration of radiation-induced G2 arrest. The underlying mechanism is currently investigated.

P22:

Air Quality Analysis in Indian Cities Using Remote Sensing and Economic Growth Parameters

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13 of the worst 20 cities in terms of air quality lie in India, as highlighted by a recent WHO report. The Indian capital, New Delhi leads the list with the worst air quality. In recent times, share of eco-health problems prevalent in various Indian cities has risen significantly resulting in a spike of respiratory and cardiac diseases. Ground measurements of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, NO₂, levels are significantly above National Ambient Air Quality Standard (NAAQS) for most cities while for New Delhi it has been found that at current rate and policies PM_{2.5} will not reach the recommended NAAQS values even by 2030. The poor state of air quality is well established and lasting policy measures are required. Therefore, an important piece of strategy to address this looming health disaster would be identifying the contributions of major causes responsible. We tackle the first piece of this problem by identifying the relationship of air quality, assessed by MODIS (from year 2001 to 2013) and OMI (from year 2005 to 2014) datasets, with economic growth parameters in the sixteen largest Indian cities by pollution. Economic growth parameters considered are urban area expansion and population growth. The results obtained after plotting correlation between various parameters are:

- a) AOD and ANG trends indicate highly polluted current urban air during summer and winter season compared to 2010 levels
- b) High ANG regression coefficients for rain and summer indicate gradually increasing contribution of anthropogenic emissions
- c) NO₂ levels increasing in all seasons pointing to seasonally invariable sources e.g. vehicle population
- d) Neighboring cities heavily influencing each other's PM levels
- e) Correlation with economic parameters indicate cities with high population have higher NO₂ levels and somewhat higher ANG and AOD levels but are witnessing decreasing SO₂ levels
- f) Growth in AOD and ANG values corresponds well with population growth and urban area of cities
- g) Good correlation between NO₂, SO₂ and AOD levels point to probable existence of common emission sources

P23:

**Molecular mechanism of anticancer activity in Embelin,
a quinone derivative of *Embelia ribes***

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Embelin is a quinone derivative, present in fruits of *Embelia ribes* (Myrsinaceae). It is known as a false black pepper in English, Vidanga in Sanskrit. In Ayurveda, it is considered widely beneficial for treatment of a variety of diseases. Therapeutic activities including anthelmintic, anti-tumor, analgesic, anti-diabetic, anti-bacterial, anti-convulsing and anti-inflammation have been reported. Inflammation is an immunological response to external harmful stimuli and is regulated by an endogenous pyrogen and pleiotropic, pro-inflammatory cytokine, tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α). The latter has been implicated in a variety of human pathologies including inflammation, neurodegeneration and cancer. Embelin has been shown to cause reduction in TNF- α levels. The latter is synthesized as a membrane anchored protein (pro-TNF α). The soluble component of pro-TNF α is then released into the extracellular space by the action of a protease called TNF- α converting enzyme (TACE). TACE has, hence, been proposed as a therapeutic target for inflammation and cancer. We found inhibition of TACE in embelin treated human breast cancer cells. We demonstrate that embelin treated cells with reduced TACE level show inhibition in growth and cancer properties including colony forming efficacy, migration and invasion that were seen to be mediated by down regulation of MMP-2, MMP-9, VEGF and hnRNP-K.

P24:**Zonal movement of Mascarene High in austral summer**Shun Ohishi¹, Shusaku Sugimoto², Kimio Hanawa²¹Department of Earth and Planetary Science, Graduate School of Science, The University of Tokyo, ²Department of Geophysics, Graduate School of Science, Tohoku University

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Temporal variations in the Mascarene High (MH), defined by the sea level pressure (SLP) maximum within the South Indian Ocean [40°–120°E, 50°–10°S] in austral summer (November–January), were investigated using NCEP–NCAR reanalysis dataset. The MH intensity has interannual variations associated with the Southern Annular Mode. The MH longitudinal position shows a longer timescale of 5–10 years compared to the intensity. It appears to be independent of the MH intensity variation because of no significant correlation between the MH intensity and longitudinal position. The MH longitudinal movement is caused by a combination of SLP variations in the eastern South Indian Ocean (ESIO) and western South Indian Ocean (WSIO). Pressure variations in the ESIO region are confined from the sea surface to the mid-troposphere, and imply association with the Matsuno–Gill response due to El Niño–Southern Oscillation. The pressure variations in the WSIO region, characterized by a quasi-barotropic structure throughout the troposphere, are related to the meridional movement of storm track.

We examine the influence of MH variations on sea surface temperature (SST) field. The MH intensity variations form a northeast-southwest dipole pattern, which resembles the climate mode called as the Indian Ocean Subtropical Dipole (IOSD). In addition, the MH longitudinal shifts also show the dipole pattern, but this is shifted 10° westward in longitude compared with that associated with the MH intensity. The correlation between the MH variations and the IOSD index show significant values (0.42 for intensity and –0.58 for longitudinal position). Therefore, it is suggested that both changes in the MH intensity and longitudinal position cause the IOSD.

P25:

Development of hexaploid wheat mutant populations through nontransgenic approach to the crop improvement

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Wheat is a major and an important dietary component across the world. IWGSC (International Wheat Genome Sequencing Consortium) was established in 2005 to make a high quality genome sequence of bread wheat, and the draft sequence of the bread wheat genome was published last year (2014). The availability of the extensive information for the wheat genome has encouraged us to develop new genetic resources as a platform to isolate important genes for basic and applied wheat research through reverse genetics approach, in addition to the traditional forward genetics approach. We have developed mutant populations of Kitahonami, Japanese cultivar of hexaploid wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) for crop improvement using two mutagens, γ -ray irradiation and ethyl methanesulfonate (EMS). About 6.9% of γ -ray irradiation mutagenized population and 5.4% of EMS mutagenized population showed a broad range of mutant phenotypes for plant/organ color, shape and size. These suggested that the development of mutated populations succeeded. For high-throughput mutant screening through reverse genetic approach, we extracted DNA from 1440 lines in γ -ray irradiation mutagenized population and 768 lines in EMS mutagenized population. The analysis of these populations will allow us to identify the novel variation useful for crop breeding. We introduce our progress of the mutant populations development and screening, and the mutant phenotypes observed in the plants.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by a grant from the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries of Japan (Genomics-based Technology for Agricultural Improvement, IVG-1003).

P26:

Project Clean World: An attempt to achieve Zero Waste in India

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Waste Generation in India and associated problems

As per 2011 census, in India 31.16% population live in urban areas, which is expected to increase to 50% by 2050. An estimated 62 million tons of municipal solid waste is being generated in urban areas, with more than 80% is disposed indiscriminately at dump yards in an unhygienic manner. This figure is projected to increase to 165 million tons by 2031 and 436 million tons by 2050 [1].

About Project Clean World

The Author¹ has lived in Tokyo for 8 years and returned recently to India in January 2014. Living in one of the cleanest mega cities in the world and then returning to India, the sharp contrast in cleanliness and pollution levels was clearly visible. **The pollution caused by waste in India is a catastrophic problem that needs immediate attention.**

Rather than government only taking initiatives to solve this problem, It is the responsibility of every resident to reduce waste generated to the minimum. For example cooperative societies in large apartments with 50 to 100 homes or more can be trained to correctly segregate and send the waste to recycling plants. Waste to Energy plants can be setups locally to avoid transport and the added problems created by transport trucks.

Pilot Efforts

As an initial step towards Project Clean World a team of Researchers, Doctors, Engineers and Students are being formed. At present we are in the process of identifying the different types of wastes being generated and what wastes can be easily recycled (like plastic bags, Glass, PET bottles, Metals, Plastic Containers like Shampoo etc.) through recycling plants already present in the city or neighboring areas. Later we plan to look at ways to safely dispose or use biodegradable wastes as bio compost, fuel for Waste to Energy plants etc.. Such integrated approach by the Citizens and Government together can minimize the waste being dumped in landfills and eventually eliminate landfills in future. The lessons learnt in India can be applied in other parts of the world.

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P27:

Facile and Rational Modulation of Ubiquitous Plant Polyphenols: Novel Multifunctional Coating Precursors from Nature

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Naturally abundant building blocks such as DNA, protein, polysaccharide, chitin, and others have been extensively studied from both fundamental perspective and wide range practical applications for decades owing to several advantages including inexpensive, wide availability, biocompatibility, and unique intrinsic properties. On the other hand, hydrosoluble plant polyphenols like catechin, tannic acid (TA) *etc* are another class of important natural raw materials found in variety of plant parts and well-known for antioxidant, antimicrobial, and other activities. Despite such wide availability and diverse scope of manipulation, chemical modifications like hydrophobization of plant polyphenols have rarely been carried out and major studies have been pursued only in aqueous media.

Recently, we developed a facile chemical modification approach to modify water-soluble tannic acid (TA) to partially *n*-alkyl (C₆, C₁₀, or C₁₆) substituted TA (PATA). Interestingly, our simple strategy enables wide range solubility of TA in organic media with broad polarity range such as *n*-hexane, chloroform, diethyl ether, ethyl acetate and others. Consequently, (ultra)thin film of PATAs was effortlessly fabricated on various metal/alloy and glass substrates. Several studies have revealed that thin-

film of PATAs are highly efficient as anticorrosion, contact based antibacterial and adhesive coatings on various substrates.

Figure (a) Chemical structure of tannic acid (TA) and some natural sources in the background. Facile chemical modification via *n*-alkylation of TA to a novel organosoluble PATA. (b) Comparison of solubility between TA & PATA in water/organic media. (c) Self-assembly of PATA on solid surfaces to a stable and multifunctional thin-film.

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P28:

The hardening source of steel: ω -Fe

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Steel, particularly carbon steel, is an ancient material. However, steel is still a new material since we do not fully understand the relationship between its microstructure and mechanical properties.

A new metastable ω -Fe with a hexagonal structure and $a \sim 0.407$ nm and $c \sim 0.248$ nm, which is similar to the ω phase in Ti and Zr alloys, has been characterized by TEM as shown in Fig. 1[1-3]. The ω -Fe has the ultrafine particle-like morphology and a special orientation relationship with bcc-ferrite as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Typical ω -Fe SAED patterns

Fig. 2. The morphology and distribution of the ω -Fe fine particles in steels.

In particular, in quenched carbon steel, there are three crystalline phases: retained austenite (fcc) with carbon, ferrite (bcc) without carbon and the ω -Fe with carbon [1]. Traditional so-called “bct” XRD pattern can be well explained by ferrite and ω -Fe in our current XRD results since an extra diffraction peak, which has a d-spacing of about

0.251nm, can be detected from quenched carbon steels. The proposed bct martensite, which appears commonly in our textbook, cannot explain this peak. With the ω -Fe, the various transformation products and microstructural evolution and mechanical properties in carbon steel can be easily understood [4].

P29:

Effect of composition on property change in ZrCuAlNi metallic glasses after high-pressure torsion

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Some bulk metallic glass (BMG) subjected to high-pressure torsion (HPT) can exhibit a less localized deformation, and decreases in hardness and elastic modulus. Such phenomenon can be attributed to structural rejuvenation characterized by an increase of atomic disorder. Meanwhile, the extent of the rejuvenation may depend on the chemical composition. In this work, we focused on BMGs with the nominal compositions of $Zr_{55}Cu_{30}Ni_5Al_{10}$ (Zr55) and $Zr_{65}Cu_{18}Ni_7Al_{10}$ (Zr65). After HPT deformation, the nanoindentation hardness and elastic modulus of Zr55 samples decreases from 6.87 ± 0.17 GPa and 105.1 ± 1.3 GPa for the as-cast sample to 5.63 ± 0.24 GPa and 92.5 ± 2.3 GPa for the N = 50 sample, respectively. The pop-in behavior in the loading segment of load-depth curves becomes less obvious with increasing rotation number. The relaxation enthalpy increases from 1.2 J/g for the as-cast sample to 12.5 J/g for the N = 50 sample. On the other hand, for the Zr65 metallic glass, the nanoindentation hardness and elastic modulus fluctuates within a narrow margin. The pop-in behavior can still be observed for the N = 50 sample. The relaxation enthalpy increases from 1.1 J/g to 8.1 J/g.

P30:

Economic Analyses of Micro-irrigation in Four Water-scarce Areas in India

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Objective: To evaluate economic benefits of drip-irrigation as a precision farming technique in four water-scarce locations in Karnataka and Maharashtra, India.

Materials and methods

Farm visits were made in Karnataka (three locations) and Maharashtra (one location) for interviewing farmers practicing drip-irrigation and recording their responses to pre-decided questionnaire

All questions were framed to gain information on pertinent qualitative and quantitative aspects

Of the 124 inputs from 99 farmers for over 35 different crops, inputs for sugarcane (n=26), arecanut (n=17), coconut (n=13), banana (n=8), pomegranate (n=14), and vegetables (n=21) were used for cost-benefit analysis.

Data available for yield, gross income, total expenditure, net income, usage of labor, water and fertilizer before and after introduction of drip irrigation for sugarcane, arecanut and coconut crops were subjected to paired t-test analyses to evaluate impact of drip-irrigation technique.

Results: There was an increase in yields observed for crops grown before and after introduction of drip practice. Both gross income and net income increased substantially, with the gross and net incomes per ha being Pomegranate (1580107± 1398741) >Vegetables (389588±517688) > Banana (350250±153864) > Arecanut (544912± 533933) > Sugarcane (397023± 205025) >Coconut (167962 ± 97038). Expenditure incurred post-drip method was at least 20% lower. Benefit: cost analysis yielded the highest ratio for Coconut (16.23) followed by Vegetables (6.42), Arecanut (6.03), Pomegranate (5.44), Sugarcane (4.23), and Banana (2.82). Mean water consumption was reduced to 53.51 (± 12.63) %. Similarly, substantial reduction in fertilizer use (mean of ~45%) and labor requirement (mean of ~60%) was also observed. Paired t-test calculated for sugarcane, areca nut and coconut crops suggest that except the less significant difference in total expenditure and fertilizer usage in the case of sugarcane, all other values were significantly different between before and after introduction of drip method.

Conclusion: This analysis signifies the importance of drip irrigation practice and highlights its beneficial effects for these crops. Many societal benefits and improved life styles were mentioned by several farmers interviewed during this survey. Therefore, drip-irrigation as a method of precision farming in terms of its profitability and environment-friendly contribution was clearly evidenced during this study.

P31:

Automated ‘PCR-on-paper’ based point-of-care-testing of infectious diseases.

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Annually, 25% of the deaths worldwide are caused by infectious diseases, out of which 95% occurs in developing countries due to lack of inaccessible diagnostics. Paper-based point-of-care (POC) devices are a new class of do-it-yourself diagnostic kits which hold great potential to deliver healthcare in low resource settings [1]. Here, we show the feasibility of isothermal amplification (Recombinase Polymerase Amplification) reaction on paper to develop an instrument-free molecular diagnostics of disease-causing DNA. RPA on paper was performed using lyophilized reagents with positive control (with DNA Template) and negative control (without DNA template) for 10 minutes and 20 minutes amplification time using a DNA template of 798bp. End point detection was done using a simple LED based transilluminator and gel electrophoresis. The product is detectable in 10 minutes in both gel electrophoresis as well as transilluminator, which suggest rapid amplification of disease causing DNA using isothermal amplification. Our results show the feasibility of RPA on paper which will be used further to develop a device integrating sample preparation, amplification and detection of amplified product in the form of color change to give a yes/no answer for the infection in blood samples.

Fig. 1 (a) Gel electrophoresis and (b) Strip of samples amplified for 10 and 20 minutes respectively (c) Fluorescence microscope image of positive and negative amplification on paper.

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P32:

Accelerated H-DROP: an SVM based helical domain linker predictor trained with features optimized by combining random forest and stepwise selection

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Domain linker prediction is the focus of much interest as it can help identifying novel domains suitable for high throughput proteomics analysis. Here, we report an accelerated version of SVM-based helical linker predictor, H-DROP (Helical Domain linker pRediction using OPTimal features). H-DROP is, to the best of our knowledge, the first predictor for specifically and effectively identifying helical linkers. The prediction sensitivity and precision of the original H-DROP were 35.2% and 38.8%, respectively, which are at least 10% higher than those of previous methods. We have now reduced the calculation time of H-DROP from about 10 minutes per sequence to ~30 seconds with minimal loss of performances (about -2%). H-DROP is freely available from <http://domserv.lab.tuat.ac.jp/>.

P33:

Engineering Silkworms For Resistance To Baculovirus Through Multigene Therapy (RNA Interference)[#]

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The sericulture industry in India is affected by various viral pathogens and cocoon crop losses. Most of the damage can be attributed to silkworm diseases rather than to unfavourable weather conditions. Prevention of silkworm diseases and breeding of a silkworm variety with high productivity are important goals of commercial sericulture. *Bombyx mori* nucleopolyhedrovirus, BmNPV is a dreaded pathogen that affects silkworm rearings and hampers cocoon production to the tune of >55% of all virus casualties. In the absence of effective management practices in place, the development of BmNPV resistant silkworm strains is the only practical alternative for enhancing the silk cocoon productivity and thus improving the standard of living of the farmers. In order to generate anti-baculovirus transgenic worms, I made use of *piggyBac* as a gene vehicle for germline mediated silkworm transgenesis. The data presented in this work supports the RNAi mediated suppression of baculoviral infection in the hybrids of transgenic silkworm lines.

Agricultural systems can sometimes be engineered for disease resistance, as I have shown by establishing stably transformed silkworms that are resistant to (BmNPV). The transformed silkworms carry RNAi constructs that target four essential viral genes, generating >75% survival of experimental viral infection relative to <15% survival in the parental strain. Even more promising, the few viral occlusion bodies derived from the transformed *B. mori* are impaired in their ability to infect naive silkworms, further limiting disease spread. As BmNPV can result in loss of >50% of commercial silk cocoon yield, the transgenic lines have great potential economic impact and were distributed to different silk stations across the country.

P34:

Environmental Impact Assessment for Infrastructure projects

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In an independent democratic civilisation, the objective of planning is not to encourage one specific style of urban living, relatively the goal of planning is to make civilised environs which will broaden the ranges open to individual city inhabitants and which will augment the numerous cultural styles that now occur. Many of the undesirable concerns of unconscious displacement of pretentious communities can be overcome by cautious planning and by providing project affected persons (PAP) with passable compensation. In this paper the resettlement system of the Chennai Port–Maduravoyal Expressway in India is revisited, concentrating on resettlers' optimistic perceptions. The procedure involving the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) of a roadway project with the help of a case study is illustrated in order to assess the changes and outcomes those have occurred in the social fabric of the affected community in similar road projects. The survey of the affected localities and population are undertaken for the better understanding of various socio-economic aspects of PAP. For forthcoming resettlement programmes, the authors recommend that policy makers should employ sustainable Resettlement and Rehabilitation package which can exactly forecast long-run effect, while local backgrounds and dynamics are imperative to be well-thought-out to secure the accomplishment of resettlement programmes.

Keywords: Resettlement, Rehabilitation, Environmental Impact Assessment, Socio-economic influence

P35:

Phase-contrast characteristics of ABF-STEM

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Recently, annular-bright-field (ABF) imaging in scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) has attracted increasing attentions, since it is extremely sensitive to detect light atom positions such as lithium and hydrogen. High-sensitivity of ABF imaging is effectively explained by its phase-contrast nature; i.e., according to reciprocity, ABF imaging is shown to be equivalent to the hollow-cone illumination (HCI) imaging in TEM [1]. Generally, the phase-contrast in conventional high-resolution TEM reveals complicated behaviors, as the image appearance varies strongly depending on the defocus values and specimen thickness. For the ABF-STEM images, these complexities seem to be significantly suppressed [2], but its phase-contrast characteristics are not fully understood yet. In the present paper, we attempt to interpret the ABF-STEM imaging based on the unique contrast-transfer-function (CTF) [3].

Although ABF-STEM is believed to be significantly robust to the contrast reversal of typical phase-contrast characteristics, it indeed occurs as demonstrated by simulations of the cubic boron-nitride (c-BN) crystal (Fig.1). The contrast reverses systematically depend on the defocus values from 0 nm to 10nm. This focus-dependence behavior of ABF-STEM cannot be simply interpreted by the conventional HCI-related CTF [2]. Alternatively, we find that such behaviors can be reasonably interpreted according to “integrated CTF” concept [3].

Fig. 1 Simulated ABF images of c-BN along $\langle 110 \rangle$, with the condition; specimen thickness 10 nm, defocus values 0, 5, 10 nm, an accelerating voltage 200 kV, a convergent semiangle 22 mrad, an inner detector semiangle 11 mrad and an outer detector semiangle 22 mrad.

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P36:

Effect of Deformation Temperature on Low-Cycle Fatigue Properties in Fe-28Mn-6Si-5Cr Shape Memory Alloy

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Fe-Mn-Si-based alloys are well known to exhibit a shape memory effect associated with a deformation-induced martensitic transformation from γ -austenite (face centered cubic structure) to ε -martensite (hexagonal close-packed structure) and its reversion on subsequent heating¹⁾. Recently, Sawaguchi *et al.* reported that Fe-Mn-Si-based alloys exhibit well low-cycle fatigue properties due to a reversible $\gamma \leftrightarrow \varepsilon$ transformation under cyclic push-pull loading²⁾. Fe-Mn-Si-based alloys show various deformation modes, which highly associates with deformation behavior, depending on the phase stabilities and the stacking fault energy of γ -austenite³⁾. Many studies of effect of chemical composition on low-cycle fatigue properties have been reported in high-Mn alloys^{2,4)}, but the effect of deformation temperature have not been reported yet. In this report, the temperature dependence of low-cycle fatigue properties of an Fe-28Mn-6Si-5Cr (mass %) shape memory alloy, as a model alloy of fatigue-resistant steel, was investigated at various temperatures. Cyclic push-pull loadings at a total strain range of 0.02 were applied to the alloy at deformation temperatures ranging from 223 to 523 K. The highest fatigue life of 22,400 cycles was obtained at 423 K. The dominant deformation modes are determined as deformation-induced martensitic transformation and ε -slip below M_s^σ , and as perfect or extended dislocation γ -slip above M_d . The highest fatigue life was obtained when the fatigue temperature lies between M_s^σ and M_d .

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P37:

Structure refinements of the LPSO-Mg alloys based on STEM imaging combined with CBED

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LPSO (Long-Period Stacking/Order) structures formed in Mg - TM (Transition Metal) - RE (Rare Earth elements) alloys are basically long-period stacking derivatives of the hexagonal close-packed (*hcp*) Mg structure. A unique long-period chemical-order occurs along the stacking direction to synchronize with the stacking order. In the LPSO structures, TM/RE atoms distribute across the four close-packed layers of local face-centered cubic (*fcc*) environments, where the L₁₂-type ordered clusters are formed [1], as shown in Fig.1. In an Mg-Zn-Y system, L₁₂-clusters relax significantly to generate a large space at the center of the clusters. The space is large enough to incorporate the interstitial atoms. First-principles calculations show that the center of the L₁₂-type clusters can be occupied by either Mg, Zn or Y atoms with a significant gain in an energetic stability [2]. In the present work, we investigate the details of the interstitial occupation behaviours based on scanning electron microscopy observations (HAADF/ABF), convergent-beam electron diffraction (CBED) analysis and first-principles calculations.

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Fig. 1 Relaxation behavior of L₁₂-type clusters in Mg-Zn-Y system [1]

P38:

Relation between Typhoon Characteristics and Climate Variations

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In recent years, the big damage by typhoon is a concern. From the IPCC AR4 report; it is likely that future tropical cyclones will become more intense with the intense peak wind speed of the ongoing rise of tropical sea surface temperatures (SST). The climate variation link to the movement, the number of approaching typhoon and landfall around Japan is not clear and not studied in detail. Therefore, the objective of this study is to examine the relation between typhoon characteristics around Japan and climate variations, and to understand ocean-atmosphere mechanisms. Relatively high correlation ($R = 0.60$) was obtained between distance of movement of typhoon and El Nino/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) index. Actually, the composites of heat content of upper 100m ocean (HC100m), SST indicate that the HC100 and SST were high around ENSO area for long movement distance of typhoons (Fig.1 (a)). And also, there were statistically significant correlations between El Nino Modoki Index (EMI), a new type of El Nino, and the typhoon genesis ($R = 0.41$), approach ($R = 0.45$) and landfall ($R = 0.32$). From the composites of sea level pressure (SLP), 200hPa geopotential height (GPH) and 850hPa wind anomalies for large number of approaching typhoons (Fig.1 (b)), it is found that an anticyclone which guides the typhoons is present off Japan. In addition to that, the 21-year sliding correlation between climate variation indices and typhoon characteristics indicate dramatic increase in the correlation after 1970s as compared to that of before 1970s. Further investigation will be carried out to find the link between climate regime shift, which causes the Pacific Ocean to suddenly change from a certain climate condition to other climate condition, and the statistical regime shift link to typhoons.

Fig.1 (a) Composites of HC100m, SST and 10m wind anomalies for long distance of movement of typhoon in 1958-2007, (b) Composites of SLP, 200hPa GPH and 850hPa wind anomalies for large number of approaching typhoon in 1958-2007

P39:

miR-335 induces apoptosis by targeting CARF in U2OS cells

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MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a class of small non-coding molecules, about 21-25 nucleotides in length, that downregulate gene expression by multiple ways, including mRNA degradation and translational block. Many studies have shown that they are involved in different biological processes, including regulation of differentiation, stress, disease pathologies and apoptosis. Here, we report an identification of miR-335 as one of the miRNAs upregulated in cells that escaped 5 AZA-dC induced senescence in human osteocarcinoma (U2OS) cells. In order to characterize the function of miR-335 in escape of senescence, we overexpressed it in a variety of human cancer cells, including U2OS, breast carcinoma (MCF7) and lung carcinoma (A549). miR-335 was seen to induce apoptosis in all of these cells. We have earlier reported that CARF (Collaborator of ARF) regulates cell senescence and apoptosis by its high and low level of expression, respectively. In this context, we anticipated that CARF may be a potential target for miR-335 and hence examined miR-335-overexpressing derivatives of U2OS, MCF7 and A549 that were triggered to apoptosis. miR-335 overexpressing cells indeed showed downregulation of CARF and its downstream effectors that triggered apoptosis. We demonstrate that miR-335 targets CARF and induces apoptosis in cancer cells.

P40:

**First-principles study on phase stability in β -type Ti-X alloys
(X = Mo, Al, Sn, Zr, Nb)**

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1. Introduction: The special quasirandom structures (SQS) model [1] has been successful in analyzing the properties of the solid solution. We studied the effect of the alloying elements on phase stability with SQS models built by *ATAT* code.

2. Computational Method: In order to assess the phase stability, free energy $F(x, T)$ was calculated by the following equation,

$$F(x, T) = E(Ti_{1-x}X_x) - TS_{config.}(x) + F_{vibr.}(x, T),$$

where, x is the molar fraction of an element X, $E(Ti_{1-x}X_x)$ is the total energy of a Ti-X alloy system calculated by *VASP* code, $S_{config.}(x)$ is the configuration entropy, and $F_{vibr.}(x, T)$ is the vibrational free energy within the framework of quasi harmonic approximation, obtained by *PHONOPY* code.

Temperature dependence of phase stability of β phase was evaluated by the mixing free energy given by

$$\Delta F^{bcc-Ref.}(x, T) = F^{bcc}(x, T) - F^{Ref.}(x, T)$$

3. Results and discussion: Compared with ordered systems, random distribution is preferred in bcc Ti alloys. The Mo, Sn and Nb stabilize the bcc in the order of Mo > Sn > Nb, while Al and Zr stabilize the hcp phase. Considering the temperature, temperature stabilizes the bcc phase strongly than the alloying elements effect.

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Access map

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